

Building the Legal Knowledge Graph for Smart Compliance Services in Multilingual Europe

D6.3 Intermediate report on communication activities

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ACRONYMS LIST

BDVA: Big Data Value Association
 LKG: Legal Knowledge Graph

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document, D6.3 “Intermediate report on communication activities”, reports on communication activities carried out from M1 to M18. It provides an update on all the communication activities performed in the five main channels set up for communicating the project: website, social media, newsletter, press releases and events. Moreover, it also provides a report on the implementation of the communication strategy, its evaluation and monitoring, and also reviews the communication plan. Finally, the last section collects recommendations and proposals for further steps in order to boost attention to the project.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable, D6.3 “Intermediate report on communication activities”, reports on communication activities carried out during the first half of the project lifespan (M1-M18). It elaborates upon the Communication Plan released in D6.1 [1]. D6.1 provided guidance to project partners regarding the communication activities, plans, methodologies, objectives and relevant audiences. The main purpose was to make the Consortium aware of the importance of the communication plan for making the Lynx project successful. Thus, D6.3 provides a report on updates in communication channels in Section 2 (website, social media, newsletter, press releases and events); communication strategy implementation, evolution and monitoring in Section 3; reviewing of the communication plan in Section 4; and, finally, it also provides recommendations and further steps in Section 5.

The second part of the project lifecycle (M18-M36) becomes crucial in terms of communication activities. From now on, it is time to communicate the project’s achievements. For instance, the Lynx’s website currently contains a “Data Portal¹” with more than 70 different datasets, a list of relevant ontologies² regarding Lynx working topics, among other relevant information and datasets that are publicly available.

This document contains a revision log table. When relevant updates occur, the revision log table will reflect the update, the date of the new revision and the author.

¹ Lynx Data Portal (CKAN): <http://data.lynx-project.eu/>

² Relevant ontologies list in Lynx website: <http://lynx-project.eu/data2/data-models/reference-ontologies>

2 COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

This Section addresses the communication channels used by Lynx to communicate the project to relevant stakeholders and end-users, as well as the general public. It is important to understand that, although the Lynx communication strategy is also directed to the general public, the technological nature of the project requires this concept of general public to be understood mainly as clients and potential clients of companies providing legal services, or using compliance services.

The first communication channel is the website, reported in Section 2.1. The **website** includes:

- a description of the project and pilots
- public documents such as public deliverables and publications
- a news section
- a section for resources that the project provides such as the data portal, data models, documents from the LKG and API services

Messages in **social media channels** for the communication of the project are reported in Section 2.2. This part of the document briefs the activities carried out through the Twitter and LinkedIn accounts created for the project.

The Lynx's **newsletter** is discussed in Section 2.3. This section goes through the contents of the newsletter, the subscribe form and the provider used to manage the newsletter subscription and the sending of e-mails. This includes compliance with data protection requirements. The first issue of the newsletter was launched in May 2019 to more than 90 subscribers.

The **press releases** are also part of Lynx's communication channels and in Section 2.4, the work done is listed.

Finally, the **events** that Lynx's partners have attended or organized are also relevant in the communication strategy. Past and future events are reported in Section 2.5. Although events are a key part of the dissemination strategy, they are also a main pillar of the communication strategy since they enable networking among Lynx partners and relevant stakeholders. And furthermore, what is even more important, events allow to publicize Lynx's communication channels through the project identity set provided in deliverable D6.1 [1] (stickers, rollup, cards, among others).

2.1 WEBSITE

The Lynx's website³ was created and launched in the first months of the project's life, as it has been already reported in D6.1. Until its release, the Consortium has continuously updated the website, and at the time of writing this document, the website counts 12.300 page views and includes different sections:

- landing page
- relevant information about the project
 - consortium
 - summary of the project's objectives
 - pilot's description
 - legal notice
 - related initiatives
- publications
 - public deliverables
 - articles

³ Lynx website available at: <http://lynx-project.eu/>

- resources provided by the Lynx project
 - data models
 - data portal
 - documents
 - services API
- news related to Lynx project

All of these sections are depicted and discussed in the next sections.

Landing page

Figure 1 shows the current landing page of the Lynx project website. It is composed of different parts, from top to bottom:

- menus top bar
- Lynx logo and full title
- objectives of the project;
- main pillars of the project: smart services, legal knowledge graph and multilingualism
- a picture that shows a model of the LKG
- pilot's brief description and a link to their specific page into the Lynx's website
- funding information
- legal notice and terms of use

Figure 1 Lynx website landing page

2.1.1 Project

The project section in the Lynx website shows relevant information about the project:

- the Consortium <http://lynx-project.eu/project/consortium>
- summary about the background and objectives of the project <http://lynx-project.eu/project/summary>
- A complete description regarding the three pilots that will be implemented in Lynx (Section 2.1.2)
- Legal notice and privacy policy <http://lynx-project.eu/project/legal>
- Related initiatives <http://lynx-project.eu/project/legal>

Figure 2 depicts the legal notice and related initiatives screenshots from the project's website.

The screenshot shows a webpage with the following content:

- Navigation:** PRIVATE, PROJECT, PUBLICATIONS, RESOURCES, NEWS
- Title:** Compliance Assurance Services in Labour Law
- Motivation:**
 - Cuatrecasas is a Spanish law firm operating internationally and advising large national and international companies on all areas of business law. One of their practice areas is labour law, where a team of lawyers provides a global service to its clients. Cuatrecasas not only advises the companies in any repercussions that their strategies might have in terms of employment relations, but it also represents and defends clients before the authorities and in courts. In this area of legal practice problems arise mainly due to transnational operations carried out by companies in different economic sectors. When dealing with these operations lawyers need to be able to advise their clients whether to undertake the venture abroad or not, bearing in mind the obligations they will have in terms of employment relations, both pre-existing and future.
 - Against this background, for lawyers to devise the best strategy in this area and best counsel their clients, they need to have an in-depth knowledge of the relevant legal framework at both EU and different countries national, and sometimes local levels. This means having access to legal provisions, case-law, administrative resolutions and expert literature. Nowadays, in order to solve these needs lawyers have to undertake a burdensome and inefficient manual work and to resort to local partner legal firms, able to provide the information related to their own jurisdictions. However, this is not cost effective in terms of both time and resources. Many companies, and sometimes public administrations themselves, already provide such services allowing lawyers to find and consult all these legal resources from different legal orders in different levels. Some of these resources, especially the main pieces of legislation, can even be found not only on the local language, but also in English, French or some other widely used language around Europe.
 - In the case of the European Union level, legislation and jurisprudence is available in the official languages of the Member States. However, this availability of vast amounts of legal data is not a guarantee of lawyers being updated on the many implications that all the legal frameworks relevant to their cases may pose. It is very difficult, and certainly inefficient in terms of use of human resources for lawyers to have to track all the news and changes that are occurring in all the relevant legal orders, when dealing with international cases. And this is especially true in the context of the common market of the European Union where more and more companies, small or big, are working in a transnational context.
 - The field of labour law poses further problems as it is by its own nature a multidimensional issue in the legal practice. Legal areas such as administrative law, commercial law, fundamental rights law, public and private international law are involved in the day-to-day business activities of customer companies. And such fields present wide divergences in terms of legal basis, legal instruments and jurisdictions. To keep track, on the daily basis, of all the different legal production, in all these sectors, in the different level of legal orders (international, European, legal) and in the different languages is an out of reach workload that can pose serious difficulties for the legal practitioners. And even more difficult is to expect them to be able to grasp, from all this myriad of legal documents, all the potential implications among them and for their own cases, in a short and useful time frame when designing and implementing their strategies. This is especially true when dealing with such a highly fragmented domain in Europe such as that of employment relations, where each country has very different regimes, procedures, and standards.
- Objectives and proposed solution:**
 - Against this background the objective within this use case is to provide access to aggregate and interlinked relevant legal information in the law labour sector across multiple legal orders, jurisdictions, and languages. This solution will leverage multilingual linked data enabling the integration of disparate legislation, administrative acts, case law, and doctrine. This proposed solution will be realised by (i) enriching the LKG with legal sources from different legal orders, countries or languages in the domain of labour law; (ii) creating extensive links (see Semantic Annotation, Extraction and Linking Services) between legal provisions, case law, administrative resolutions and expert literature even across different jurisdictions; (iii) offering a tailored service for lawyers that effectively identify the relevant documents that may affect the case they are handling in a more efficient way (see Recommender and Alert Services) and (iv) creating alerts, through the life cycle of the case, of news and relevant changes to any of the legal provisions or documents that the lawyer working the case has identified as applicable or of interest for the case. The pilot will cover the different jurisdictions (EU, DE, AT, IT, ES). The prototype will improve the existing systems at the law firm in the following regards:
 - More complete identification of all the relevant legal provisions in terms of employment in order to give informed advice to the client on the viability of the country.
 - Favours a better informed strategy definition for the internationalisation of companies, as Lynx will enable the fast identification and comparison of all the relevant legislation and case-law to handle the labour aspects.
- Footer:**
 - This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 750622.
 - in
 - Website developed by CEO-LP4. Legal Information
 - T3 Framework Modern and Public Research
 - Bootstrap is a front-end framework of Twitter, Inc. Code licensed under MIT License.
 - Font Awesome font licensed under SIL OFL 1.1.

Figure 3 Lynx Pilots description in the Lynx website

2.1.3 Publications

Publications (deliverables, articles and press releases) are also a main pillar in the communication strategy. These publications enable communication among the Lynx project and different target audiences considered in D6.1 [1]: academia, SMEs, LEs and EU citizens. The publications section in the Lynx website includes: public report deliverables and, articles and press releases.

Public report deliverables

In order to fulfil the H2020 requirements, public report deliverables require Open Access to be provided free of charge by Lynx partners; thus, making it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate the results obtained (see deliverable D2.1 [2]). Therefore, all public report deliverables are uploaded to Zenodo⁴ and also linked in the “Public report deliverables” Lynx website page (Figure 4): <http://lynx-project.eu/publications/deliverables>.

⁴ Lynx community in Zenodo available at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/lynx?page=1&size=20>

Figure 4 Lynx public report deliverables

Table 1 reports the number of views and downloads of public reports uploaded to Zenodo.

Report name	Views	Downloads	Upload date
D1.1 Functional Requirements Analysis Report	105	256	May 31, 2018
D1.2 Technical Requirements Analysis Report	37	36	November 30, 2018
D1.3 Technical Architecture Design	25	21	February 28 2019
D2.1 Initial Data Management Plan	101	85	May 31, 2018
D2.2 Intermediate report on Lynx acquired vocabularies	29	27	November 30, 2018
D2.3 Intermediate report on Lynx acquired corpora	6	6	April 30, 2019
D3.1 Intermediate extraction and linking services	27	25	February 28, 2019
D3.2 Intermediate translation services	21	27	February 28, 2019
D4.1 Pilots Requirements Analysis Report	131	82	May 31, 2018
D4.2 Initial version of workflow definition	23	27	November 30, 2018
D6.1 Website, project identity set, and communication plan	103	72	April 27, 2018

Table 1 Lynx documents' views and downloads in Zenodo

Articles and press releases

Moreover, the “Publications” section in the Lynx website also contains links to the five articles published by Lynx partners in workshops and conferences. Finally, the press release already published is also listed in this page. Figure 5 shows a screenshot of this page in the Lynx website.

Figure 5 Articles and press releases in the Lynx website

2.1.4 Resources

This part of the Lynx website is where the resources developed by Lynx partners become available in order to make them openly accessible. The publication of these resources is based on a strategy that relies on two main pillars: i) to communicate project achievements to stakeholders; and ii) to ease the engagement of these stakeholders to the project.

Legal Language Resources⁵

Given the multilingual nature of Lynx compliance services, a sound basis of language resources of the legal and regulatory domain needs to be shaped. Such language resources are to be used to annotate, classify and translate the legal documents that will be part of the LKG. Figure 6 shows a screenshot of this part of the Lynx website.

Relevant ontologies⁶

Relevant ontologies for the project are also listed in the Lynx website. In this list, the ontology name, type of document, name, description, language and jurisdiction are reported. Figure 7 depicts a screenshot of this page on the project website.

Data portal⁷

In the “Resources” section of the Lynx website, there is also available a data portal that contains more than 60 datasets. This portal includes the possibility to launch a query to all datasets. Figure 8 shows a screenshot of the data portal on the Lynx website and Figure 9 shows a screenshot of the answer to the query “labour law” (third pilot foreseen in the project). In the answer, all related datasets are provided, even more, name, description and format of data are also included.

⁵ Lynx Legal Language Resources available at: <http://lynx-project.eu/data2/data-models/diagrams>

⁶ Relevant ontologies for the Lynx Project available at: <http://lynx-project.eu/data2/data-models/reference-ontologies>

⁷ Lynx Data Portal available at: <http://data.lynx-project.eu/>

Figure 8 Lynx Data Portal

Figure 9 Lynx Data Portal answers to the query “Labour Law”

Multilingual Legal Knowledge Graph⁸

Then, a small Lynx pilot to demonstrate how access to legislation as data within the Multilingual Legal Knowledge Graph have been implemented. Figure 10 depicts a screenshot of the Multilingual Legal Knowledge Graph at the time of writing this report.

Service API⁹

Finally, the last part of the Lynx website resources section consists of the service APIs description that at the time of writing this report is only intended for internal use of Lynx partners.

Figure 10 Lynx Multilingual Legal Knowledge Graph

⁸ Lynx Multilingual Knowledge Graph available at: <http://lkg.lynx-project.eu/>

⁹ Lynx Service API available at: <http://lynx-project.eu/doc/api>

Figure 11 Lynx API descriptions

2.1.5 News

This section contains the “News” site within the Lynx website. In this section, the Lynx Consortium publishes all relevant information regarding project events (meetings, conferences and workshops organized and attended) achievements, and published data sets, among others. This section is intended to communicate relevant news from the project to stakeholders, end-users and general public. Figure 12 depicts a screenshot of this section. At the time of writing this report, more than 35 news had been already published in this section.

The screenshot shows the Lynx website's news section. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for PRIVATE, PROJECT, PUBLICATIONS, RESOURCES, and NEWS. The main content area features several news items:

- 4th Lynx Plenary Meeting being celebrated in Barcelona:** A large article with a photo of a meeting. The text states that about twenty members of the Lynx Consortium are meeting in Barcelona from April 29th to 30th to recap the project status and address new action points. The meeting is hosted by Cuatrecasas and is a crucial appointment since the project is now in month 17. It is the middle of the project, time to carefully select the next steps in order to accomplish fixed goals and milestones. The Advisory Board, composed of Philipp Cimiano, Marie-Claude L'Homme and Neil Wilkof, attended as well (present and online). They raised useful questions and enriching suggestions that will for sure be of great help to boost the project.
- Lynx partner co-organising a workshop at ISWC 2019:** A shorter article with a logo for Auckland 2019 ISWC. It mentions that the workshop proposal sent to ISWC 2019, co-organised by Elena Montiel-Ponsoda, Lynx partner from UPM, has been accepted. The workshop is called International Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Big Data Technologies for Legal Documents (AILEGAL) and it is also being co-organised by Manolis Koutarakis (University of Athens), Giorgos Antoniou (University of Huddersfield), Guido Governatori (GATE 61 - CQRI) and Yashenou Kano (Jozefua University). AILEGAL will be held during the International Semantic Web Conference (29th-30th October 2019) in Auckland, New Zealand. See website for more details.
- Successful presentation of Lynx project:** A shorter article with a photo of a presentation. It states that Christian Saegjerd from Operative attended the Ciolex workshop within the IS conference celebrated last week (21st-23rd of February) in Salzburg, where he presented Lynx initiative for multijurisdictional legal compliance.
- Lynx Coding Sprint taking place in Cercedilla:** A shorter article with a photo of a group of people. It states that during this week, several collaborators of Lynx initiative are staying at UPM's facilities in Cercedilla to work in the different packages of the project. This "coding sprint week" started on Monday and will be finished on Friday, 1st of March. Representatives of Semantic Web Company, Openlaws, DFKI, TIKO, K Dictionaries, Argentina, Universidad de Zaragoza and Universidad Politécnica de Madrid are joining efforts to take the most of these days and reach consistent results.
- Lynx will be presented to CodeX, the Stanford Legal Tech Group:** A shorter article with the CodeX logo. It states that CodeX, the Stanford Group of Legal Informatics, will be attending the IS conference that takes place in Salzburg, during the 21st-23rd of February. Partners of Lynx Consortium will present the project to this group on Thursday 21st.

At the bottom of the news section, there is a "More Articles ..." section with a list of links: "4th Lynx Plenary Meeting in Barcelona", "Upcoming Event: Lynx Coding Sprint", "TeReCom Workshop celebrated in Groningen", and "Lynx Plenary Meeting is taking place in Vienna". Below this is a pagination control showing "Page 1 of 7".

The footer of the website contains the following information:

- This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant Agreement No 75562.
- Website developed by CEO-UPM.
- T3 Framework: Modern and Flexible Framework.
- RSS: Bootstrap is a front-end framework of Twitter, Inc. Code licensed under MIT License.
- Font Awesome font licensed under SIL OFL 1.1.

Figure 12 News section in the Lynx website

2.2 SOCIAL MEDIA

As stated in D6.1 [1], the social networks strategy for the Lynx project relies on four main pillars. The first is a Twitter account that is a social network focused on a general and diversified nature of topics. Thus, the Twitter account has been used to disseminate project achievements and events in order to reach all the identified key end-users and stakeholders as well as the general public. The second pillar is the LinkedIn account. This social media channel focuses on B2B, companies and enterprises. Thus, it is an important way of communication to be in touch and interplay with businesses stakeholders. The third pillar consists of the SlideShare account. This account is focused on the sharing of presentations and visual material. It is mainly addressed to an academic audience, allowing the definition of a considerable set of keywords and consistent descriptions of each audio-visual material, facilitating the search of specific content and, consequently, increasing the degree of expert acquaintance with the project. Finally, the

fourth pillar consists of a YouTube channel to promote upcoming events, webinars, and achievements, among other contents.

2.2.1 Twitter

Lynx has set up a Twitter account <https://twitter.com/lynxh2020?lang=en> with the user name: @lynxh2020. Through this account, the project has been sharing results, meetings, conferences, public events and, to sum it up, all its relevant achievements and events. In addition, the Twitter account enables comments and feedback from researchers, stakeholders and potential consumers. Figure 13 shows a screenshot of the twitter account at the time of writing this deliverable.

Figure 13 Lynx Twitter account

Table 2 shows statistics regarding tweets, following, followers and tweets with multimedia content. Moreover, Figure 14 depicts a 28 days summary of the Lynx twitter account where “Impressions” means number of times users saw the tweet on Twitter.

Tweets	Following	Followers	Media
66	36	137	8

Table 2 Lynx twitter account statistics

Figure 14 Lynx twitter account 28 days summary with change over previous period

Figure 15 depicts the top tweets ordered by number of impressions. In this figure, “Impressions” means the number of times users saw the tweet on Twitter. “Engagements” is the total number of times a user has interacted with a tweet, this includes all clicks anywhere on the tweet (including hashtags, links, avatar, user name and tweet expansion), retweets, replies, follows and likes. “Engagement rate” means

the number of engagements (clicks, retweets, replies, follows and likes) divided by the total number of impressions.

Tweets	Top Tweets	Tweets and replies	Promoted	Impressions	Engagements	Engagement rate
	H2020 Lynx Project @lynxH2020 · Apr 30	Thank you @Cuatrecasas for the organization of the 4th Lynx Plenary Meeting in #Barcelona Amazing work during the plenary and amazing sights. @BDVA_PPP pic.twitter.com/qhEmcA74uo		2,935	142	4.8%
	H2020 Lynx Project @lynxH2020 · May 7	@unizar and K Dictionaries organize the 2nd shared task for Translation Inference Across Dictionaries (TIAD 2019) aimed at exploring methods and techniques for automatically generating new bilingual (and multilingual) dictionaries from existing ones. tiad2019.unizar.es		1,033	3	0.3%
	H2020 Lynx Project @lynxH2020 · May 7	Subscribe to @lynxH2020 newsletter in this link: landing.mailerlite.com/webforms/landi... #1 of LYNX's newsletter will be launched next week! @BDVA_PPP		684	15	2.2%
	H2020 Lynx Project @lynxH2020 · May 7	Our colleague Francesc Muñoz Molina from @Cuatrecasas will take part in the session "Artificial Intelligence for Legal Professional Practice" at the Spanish National Congress of the Legal Profession 2019 @BDVA_PPP registro.congresoabogacia.es/ae2019/es/Cust...		457	17	3.7%
	H2020 Lynx Project @lynxH2020 · May 7	@accio_cat took part in the @lynxH2020 Advisory Board session during the 4th Plenary Meeting that was held in Barcelona (29th - 30th of April 2019). Thank you @accio_cat for your valuable feedback		34	1	2.9%
	H2020 Lynx Project @lynxH2020 · 4m	Our partners from @semwebcompany will hold a @lynxH2020 technical meeting in #Vienna on May 22-23, 2019. In this meeting, technical partners will decide on several issues that have raised during the project development. These decisions will allow a smooth run of the project.		13	1	7.7%

Figure 15 Lynx top tweets statistics

2.2.2 LinkedIn

The Lynx project set up a LinkedIn profile page available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/lynx-project-h2020/>. The profile contains basic information about the project, its main objectives and the Consortium, including links to the partners profile pages in LinkedIn. Here the Lynx project has been sharing results, meetings, conferences, public events and, in summary, all relevant achievements and events related to Lynx. The main goal is to increase acquaintance with the project by the professional community within this social network. Figure 16 shows the LinkedIn account landing page.

Figure 16 Lynx LinkedIn account

At the time of writing this deliverable, the Lynx LinkedIn account has 65 connections and 37 profile viewers in the last 90 days. Figure 17 depicts a graphic that represents the views during the last 90 days.

Figure 17 Lynx LinkedIn account profile viewers in the last 90 days

2.2.3 SlideShare

The Lynx project set up a SlideShare profile available at: <https://www.slideshare.net/LynxProject>. This channel is being used to share information about the project using presentations. The main goal of this tool is to increase audience awareness levels and to spread out the project results and achievements, therefore, during the next months the Lynx consortium is planning to make an effort to produce infographics, documents, videos and even more presentations to be uploaded.

At the time of writing this report, one presentation is uploaded to the Lynx SlideShare account, counting more than 80 views in the last year. Figure 18 depicts a summary of how these visits were distributed over the last year.

Figure 18 Lynx SlideShare views in the last year

2.2.4 YouTube

The Lynx YouTube channel, at the time of writing this report, has no content uploaded yet. However, according to recommendations stated in Section 5.1 for the next phase of the project, several video interviews are now being prepared and will be recorded shortly. These media material will start with contributions from members of the Consortium. After that, these videos will be uploaded to the website and YouTube Lynx channel.

2.3 NEWSLETTERS

A newsletter is a report containing news of the activities of a business or organization that is sent by e-mail regularly to those who are interested in. The Lynx project has released a newsletter that summarises all the activities carried out during a specific period of time (Section 2.3.1). Moreover, the Lynx consortium also contributed to other newsletters to disseminate and communicate its achievements to different stakeholders (Section 2.3.2).

2.3.1 Lynx newsletter

One of the main communication channels used by the Lynx project is the Newsletter. Issue #1 of the newsletter was launched on May 16th, 2019. It contains a mix of Lynx project description, events attended and organized by Lynx partners, meetings between Lynx partners, data sources made openly accessible by the Lynx project, and other activities such as accepted papers on conferences or workshops. Moreover, the newsletter is also useful to disseminate tools that the Lynx project has been working out. For instance, the LKG¹⁰ and the API services¹¹ that are available at the Lynx website.

After an exhaustive review of newsletter providers in the market, the Lynx Consortium has finally chosen MailerLite¹². MailerLite is a simple email marketing solution for all types of businesses. The key idea behind this solution is simplicity. It provides a simple and user-friendly content editor, simplified subscriber management, and campaign reports with the most important statistics. In addition, accounts with less than 1,000 subscribers and less than 12,000 e-mails/month are free of charge. Thus, the use of MailerLite as a newsletter distribution tool does not impact on the budget of the project.

¹⁰ Lynx LKG available at: <http://lkg.lynx-project.eu/>

¹¹ Lynx API services available at: <http://lynx-project.eu/api/doc/>

¹² MailerLite available at: <https://www.mailerlite.com/>

Figure 19 Dashboard screenshot of the MailerLite Lynx account

Figure 19 shows the dashboard of the MailerLite Lynx account. It provides useful information such as unique subscribers, subscribers growth, e-mails sent in the current month, and others.

Figure 20 Subscribers screenshot of the subscribers' screen in the MailerLite Lynx account

Figure 20 depicts the “Subscribers” tab on the MailerLite tool. It contains helpful information about the communication process such as a list of all subscribers (only e-mail is stored), total number of subscribers, statistics (shown in Figure 21) and it also offers the possibility of segmenting subscribers. However, the Lynx team is no yet using this functionality.

Figure 21 Subscribers’ statistics in the MailerLite Lynx account

Figure 22 Right: Subscribe form to the Lynx newsletter; Left: Confirmation e-mail and verification once an individual fill in the subscribe form

Figure 22 (Right) depicts the Lynx newsletter subscribe form available at: <http://lynx-project.eu/join-us/newsletter>. A legal notice has been included in the subscribe form explaining the collection of personal data. In particular, this subscribe form requires the e-mail as the only information needed to subscribe to the newsletter. It also contains information about the permissions that the subscriber grants regarding

the use of her/his e-mail. In addition, the subscribe form also reports that MailerLite is the company that will handle the e-mails and it is also possible to check MailerLite’s privacy policy and terms of use. The Lynx Consortium has reviewed the privacy policy and the terms of use and none of them raises any ethical concern. Moreover, MailerLite is an entity based-on Europe, therefore, it complies with the European General Data Protection Regulation and all relevant legislation at the EU level

2.3.2 Lynx contribution to other newsletters

KD Newsletter

On July 2018, Lynx partners contributed to Kernerman Dictionary (KD) newsletter. This newsletter covers a wide range of topics related to terminology and lexicography. The text is available at: https://kdictionaries.com/kdn/kdn26_2018.pdf pages 2-5 [3]. Moreover, the Lynx Consortium is planning to update this contribution during 2019.

BDVA Newsletter

The Lynx Consortium is also preparing a contribution to the BDVA newsletter¹³. At the time of writing this report, the contribution is not yet ready, but it will be included in one of the next issues.

2.4 PRESS RELEASES

The Lynx Consortium has contributed to one press release that introduces the project in one of the most relevant online publications about innovation in Spanish¹⁴. The press release can be found online [4].

2.5 EVENTS

Events attended and organized by Lynx partners for the period M1-M18 are reported in Table 3 and for the period M18-M24 in Table 4. These events are relevant from a communication point of view since they enable the communication of the project and to distribute the project identity set provided in D6.1 [1].

Date	Event
November 13-14, 2017, Brussels (Belgium)	META-FORUM
December 13, 2018, Luxemburg (Luxemburg)	Jurix 2017 - International conference on Legal Knowledge and Information Systems (1st Workshop on Technologies for Regulatory Compliance)
February 17, 2018, Ljubliana (Slovenia)	Elexis kick-off meeting - European Lexicographic Infrastructure
April 17, 2018, Vienna (Austria)	Data Privacy W3C Workshop
May 3-4, 2018, Madrid (Spain)	PDP4E kick-off meeting - Privacy and Data Protection for Engineers
May 14-15, 2018, Sofia (Bulgaria)	Big Data Value Meet-up
May 7-12, 2018, Miyazaki (Japan)	LREC - International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (Workshop on Language Resources and Technologies for the Legal Knowledge Graph)
May 18-19, 2018, Beijing (China)	GAITC - The Global Artificial Intelligence Technology Conference
June 3-7, 2018, Crete (Greece)	Extended Semantic Web Conference
September 10-13, 2018, Vienna (Austria)	Semantics Conference

¹³ BDVA newsletter available at: <http://bdva.eu/node/839>

¹⁴ Innovaspain.com available at: <https://www.innovaspain.com/>

September 19, 2018, Barcelona (Spain)	Fabra avui conference
October 2, 2018, Brussels (Belgium)	EUDATATHON
November 5-7, 2018, Madrid (Spain)	ECETT conference - Encuentros Complutenses en torno a la Traducción
November 12-14, 2018, Vienna (Austria)	European BIG DATA VALUE Forum
February 21-23, 2019, Salzburg (Austria)	IRIS Conference (Internationales Rechtsinformatik Symposium)
December 12, 2018, Groningen (The Netherlands)	TeReCom Workshop celebrated in Groningen (Organized by Lynx partners)
March 20, 2019, Boston (USA)	Enterprise Data World in Boston
April 29-May 1, Melbourne (Australia)	Conference on Law and Technology
May 2, Melbourne (Australia)	Post-Conference Symposium. The Regulation of the Web of Linked Data.
May 20-23, 2019, Leipzig (Germany)	LDK 2019 – 2 nd Conference on Language, Data and Knowledge
May 20, 2019, Leipzig (Germany)	TIAD 2019 – Translation Inference Across Dictionaries

Table 3 Events attended and co-organised by Lynx partners during M1-M18 period

Date	Event
June 2-6, 2019, Portorož (Slovenia)	ESWC 2019 - Extended Semantic Web Conference
June 6-7, 2019, Minneapolis (USA)	Workshop on Natural Legal Language Processing (NLLP) co-located with NAACL 2019 - Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics
June 8, 2019, Madrid (Spain)	LegalHackers Madrid Meet-up
June 24-25, 2019, Brussels (Belgium)	8th Language Technology Industry Summit
June 26-28, 2019, Riga (Latvia)	BDV PPP Meetup 2019 - Big Data Value Public-Private Partnership
August 10-16, 2019, Macao (China)	IJCAI 2019 - International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence
August 26-29, 2019, Linz (Austria)	International Workshop on Machine Learning and Knowledge Graphs
September 9-12, 2019, Karlsruhe (Germany)	SEMANTICS 2019
October 8-9, 2019, Brussels (Belgium)	META-FORUM 2019
October 26-30, 2019, Auckland (New Zealand)	AI4LEGAL workshop at International Semantic Web Conference
December 11-13, 2019, Madrid (Spain)	JURIX 2019 - International Conference on Legal Knowledge and Information Systems

Table 4 Events that Lynx partners are planning to attend and co-organise for M18-M24 period

3 COMMUNICATION STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION, EVOLUTION AND MONITORING

The communication strategy was established at the kick-off meeting and reviewed at every plenary meeting of the project. The partners supported project communication by sharing information as well as by proactively providing content.

Lynx website contents have been growing (see Section 2.1), social media channels have been increasing their impact among relevant stakeholders, end-users and general public (see Section 2.2), the first issue of the Lynx newsletter has been launched (see Section 2.3) and Lynx partners have attended and organized several conferences and meetings during the first half of the project (see Section 2.5). Additionally, the Consortium is already working on a set of videos that will be published in the Lynx YouTube channel. These videos will explain:

- the Lynx project as a whole
- objectives and main features of Lynx project
- services that Lynx partners are already developing and the added value of Lynx for the business cases, among others.

Moreover, in order to achieve the highest quality of the impact of the activities for the communication, the following steps were taken to monitor the communication strategy:

- Virtual meetings every month as part of the plenary telco
- The decisions that were taken in both virtual and in-person meetings are documented in the meeting minutes that are available to project partners
- Exchange of information and content through the mailing list and shared documents in the NextCloud platform
- Review of the communication strategy in each plenary meeting

4 REVIEWING THE COMMUNICATION PLAN

In the last plenary meeting held in April 29th and 30th, 2019, the Consortium devoted a full session to the revision of WP6; it was decided to take a series of new steps and improvements based on the analysis of the strengths and weakness of the communication plan. The main target of these initiatives is to optimize and improve information, and to renew the commitment of all partners. Thus, the Consortium agreed to:

- Create a communication reporting file in the NextCloud platform
- Send a monthly reminder to all partners to provide content for communication
- Provide a set of videos discussing different subjects of the Lynx project for the YouTube channel
- Initiate discussions on the organization of the Lynx final event

Figure 23 shows a screenshot of the Lynx communication reporting file. This file contains one tab per partner in the project and each row represents one month in the project lifespan. Each partner has committed to propose at least one communication activity per month.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
6		April 2019					
		Tech Meeting in Vienna May 22-23	Event organization	Vienna May 22-23	most technical partners	technical meeting to decide on certain issues in the project progress	
7		June 2019 ESWC paper	Publication	Portoroz June 1-6	SWC	Poster to be presented. Topic: question answering	
8		July 2019					

Figure 23 Lynx Communication reporting file

5 RECOMMENDATIONS AND FURTHER STEPS

Recommendations for the upcoming phase of the project are mainly focused on the consolidation of the tools and distribution channels already created (website, social media, newsletter, press releases and events). Moreover, the Consortium foresees a final project event to disseminate and communicate the results of the Lynx project.

5.1 CONSOLIDATION

Main recommendations for the consolidation of the tools and distribution channels are:

- Press releases: The Lynx Consortium should consider proactive collaboration with Commission press officers and other public administration bodies to ensure communication via EC and similar channels, but will mainly focus on the envisaged industry target groups that will be the end users of the Lynx platform
- Video interviews: starting with members of the Consortium, these videos will be uploaded to the website and YouTube Lynx channel
- Events connections: link every event of your organization to Lynx: all events related to the Lynx project should be linked to the project through any of the communication channels available

Following these recommendations, the Lynx Consortium expects to boost attention to the project.

5.2 LYNX FINAL EVENT

The organization of a Lynx final event raises some questions that should be answered by the Consortium. The most important issue is to decide what concept the Consortium wants to pursue. Moreover, there are three different possible approaches to the Lynx final event with their pros and cons: Lynx own event, broader event with other sister projects, half day event in a major conference in the field.

Table 5 lists the pros and cons regarding a Lynx own final event. If the Consortium decides to pursue this approach the next step should be to give an answer to the following questions: Who hosts? Duration? Targeted speakers?

Pros	Cons
The Consortium can shape it as it pleases	More expensive
The Consortium chooses the date	More effort
More visibility for the project	Are we able to engage enough audience?

Table 5 Pros and cons of a final Lynx event

Table 6 shows the pros and cons of the option of a Lynx final event shared with other sister projects. In addition, other open questions of this approach are: Identify potential sister projects and evaluate their interest in this approach.

Pros	Cons
Shared costs	Date and content to be negotiated
Broader audience	Less focus on Lynx

Table 6 Pros and cons of a final Lynx event shared with sister projects

Table 7 shows the pros and cons regarding a Lynx final event in a major conference in the field of big data and artificial intelligence. In addition, other open question this approach is to identify potential events that fit into Lynx timeframe.

Pros	Cons
Free or cheap	Needs to be accepted as parallel event
Broader audience	Less focus on Lynx
Possibility of a booth at a Legal Tech fair?	

Table 7 Pros and cons of a final Lynx event in a major conference in the field

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